

THE READING CULTURE OF ENGLISH MAJORED STUDENTS AT TAY DO UNIVERSITY, VIETNAM

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Abstract:

In the 21st century, the development of many modern entertainment facilities makes people rarely focus on reading books. So, the reading culture gradually fell into oblivion. In reality, when teachers ask students about their reading habit, students often say “we seldom read books”, they mostly read books because of teacher requests or school assignments. Therefore, the research “The reading culture of English majored students at Tay Do University” was conducted with the purpose of helping English linguistic students to acknowledge the importance of reading books. Thanks to this, they can find their own situations and spend more time reading books. The participants of this study were 100 English majored students of four classes including English Linguistic 10B, 11A, 12C and 13A at Tay Do University that were chosen randomly. The instrument used in this thesis was the questionnaire. The data from questionnaires were statistically analyzed by SPSS English version 20.0 package. Based on research results, the researcher found out some common students’ thoughts on reading culture as well as solutions to develop their reading culture in the future.

Keywords: reading culture, students’ attitudes towards reading, reading habit, university students

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Chapter I: Introduction

Chapter I presents rationale, the aims of the research, the questions of the research, significance of the study and the organization of the thesis.

1.1 Rationale

Books are kith and kin, they are like our teachers, counselors, advisors or close friends... It can be said that a good book is a lighthouse that enlightens our minds, families, schools and societies, it does not only educate hearts, improve characters, console but also delights us. The deeper people delve into reading, the more they are drawn to it. Reading is a nice choice to relax and de-stress after a hard-working day. Books do not only entertain us, provide valuable knowledge but also sharpen our intellect. Moreover, reading books encourages imagination and enhances vocabulary as well. *"A room without books is like a body without a soul"* (Marcus Tullius Cicero – 1966).

In the 21st century - the era of industrialization and modernization, social media development has many impacts in human's life. As people have various sources to get information or to entertain ourselves through internet, television and radio, the healthy reading habit seems to fade away. Young people, especially students do not understand completely the endless value of reading books. Before finding out the importance of reading book, we need to know the concept of reading, *"in simple words, it is a process of interpreting printed and written words. In depth, it is an effective process of conscious learning that influences the accuracy of information, attitudes, morals, beliefs, judgments and action of readers"* (Panigrahib & Panda, 1996). If reading is considered as a key, books are treasures which need this key to open the doors of knowledge. *"Reading is important. If you know how to read, then the whole world opens up to you"* (Barack Obama, 2013).

It can be seen that reading books plays a major role in acquiring knowledge and developing our characteristics, especially for students. *"Reading is a way to get better knowledge of one's own experiences and it can be an exciting journey to self-discovery. It transfers experiences to the individual so that the reader may expand one's horizons, identify, extend and intensify his or her interest and gain deeper understanding of the world"* (Green, 2002). This skill is regarded as *"one of the most important components in learning language and it is an essential tool for lifelong learning for all learners"* (Pandian, 1997; Mokatsi, 2005). Knowing the value of books but people still belittle reading books, especially students.

In fact, students are bored with reading books or reading seems to be their last choice for entertainment. They tend to choose other kinds of entertainment rather than reading books. In my opinion, if students read books, they can create a habit of reading books and can access all the book's knowledge at a very young age. It can be wondered that their parents always focus on earning money. They often buy their children modern and expensive toys to play. In reality, some children just stick to online games on their parents' phones. Meanwhile, there are very few families with bookcases. For those who live in farming families, they have low living conditions and lack of knowledge about book values. They think that the books are too high to buy. Besides, the majority of books

in school libraries are textbooks and research books (students aren't keen on these) while books for teenagers or history books are really scarce.

At present, young people have a lot of information channels for entertainment, the Internet is widely installed, electronic newspapers are immense, social networks have attracted young people recently, so more and more students are familiar with online reading habits. Sadly, students - the owners of the society's future are very indifferent to the hidden treasure of knowledge - books. Typically, my classmates rarely read books, they have little contact with books, when they need an answer, they immediately use their smartphones to search on google and do not need to think carefully or contemplate that answer. I think that our reading habits has fallen into oblivion.

For the reasons above, the study "*The reading of English majored students at Tay Do University*" was carried out to explain these issues more clearly. The researcher conducted this study with the aim of encouraging English majored students reading books as well as knowing the value of good books.

1.2 Research aims and research questions

The purpose of this study is to describe the reading culture among English majored students at Tay Do University. Findings from this study will provide insights into the reading behaviors of these students. More importantly, we can find out some methods which attract students to read.

The research was done to answer the following questions:

Q1: How is the reading culture of English majored students at Tay Do University?

Q2: What are the students' attitudes toward reading?

Q3: What are some important solutions to attract students to read?

1.3 Significance of the research

The research is conducted with the purpose of encouraging students to spend time on reading books. Particularly, based on the result, students know more clearly about the reasons why they are bored with reading books. Thanks to recognizing their own issues, students can enjoy reading more books.

1.4 The organization of the research

Chapter I: Introduction

Chapter II: Literature review

Chapter III: Research methodology

Chapter IV: Results and Discussion

Chapter V: Conclusion, implications, limitations,

Chapter VI: Recommendations for future research

Chapter II: Literature Review

Chapter II explains the definitions of reading and its importance to readers; the definitions of reading culture and the relationship between reading and reading culture; some previous research papers; how reading culture affects learning outcomes.

2.1 Definition of reading and its importance

2.1.1 Definition of reading

There are many concepts of reading from various researchers. Firstly, according to William (1984), *“reading as a process whereby one looks at and understands what has been written”*. Rohani Ariffin (1992) stated *“reading as a highly personal activity that is mainly done silently, alone. There is a clear understanding that reading is something related to the activity of acquiring information and it is done either silently or aloud”*. It is also said *“reading as a two-way interaction in which information is exchanged between the reader and the author”* (Brown, 1989). In addition, Smith (1973) also shares the same idea *“reading is an act of communication in which information is transferred from a transmitter to a receiver”*. Despite all the given definitions, there is a definition of reading given by Stallfter (1969), *“A complicated procedure. Readers read to get information from the printed pages. They should be able to pronounce and comprehend the printed words, signs, letters, and symbols by assigning meaning to them”*. However, there are two explanations of reading in Longman Dictionary of Applied Linguistic including *“Perceiving a written text in order to understand its contents. This can be done silently (silent reading). The understanding that result is called reading comprehension”* and *“Saying a written text aloud (oral reading). This can be done with or without understanding of the content”*. In my opinion, reading is an act of looking at books and understanding the information, meaning and message of these books. Different researchers have their own ideas of reading, but most of them think that reading is a supporting skill to improve some other skills in acquiring English.

2.1.2 The importance of English reading skill

Researchers have discussed the importance of reading skill in many fields. Reading skill improves our linguistic ability. *“Besides gains in reading comprehension, vocabulary growth, spelling ability, grammatical usage and writing style, students who read well are able to access more texts and knowledge through wide and varied reading”* (Cunningham and Stanovich, 1998).

There's a saying *“knowledge is power”* (Bacon, 1657). Without reading, people lack knowledge. In communication, English learners also need knowledge and we get knowledge from reading. Without reading, how can people share their knowledge? How can people know what is happening in this world? How can people talk well without experience and make knowledge? All of this derives from reading. According to Chickie Momma, 1961), *“Reading is important because it affects your whole life and everything you do”*. Want to drive? You have to know how to read signs, handbooks, testing materials, etc. Want to buy a house? You have to know how to read that contract unless they want to be ripped off! Every contract you ever sign, from leases to credit cards, to loans, need to be

read. In the modern world, we all accept that *“reading is a very important aspect of life which is not only about enjoyment but a necessity; the basic tool of education. Reading is key for each and every human being in order to deal with new and emerging knowledge in the changing world of technological advances”* (Tella and Akande, 2007).

2.2 Definition of reading culture and the relationship between reading and reading culture

2.2.1 The concept of reading culture

In the age of information technology, young people can get bad influences. The reading culture is one of many hot issues in our society. There are many ideas of reading culture. *“Reading culture is the reading behavior, value and standard of each individual, these include three components: reading habit, reading hobby and reading skill”* (National Library of Vietnam-2010). A Vietnamese poet Mai Nam Thang said *“Reading culture is the attitude of individuals and communities to read books”*. According to MA Pham Van Tinh, *“Reading culture is our attitude, our behavior with book knowledge. We have to read by reasonable and useful ways”*. Besides, *“Reading habits, the ability to choose and reading skill combine together and create what we call reading culture”* was stated by author Chu Hao. In addition, writer Pham Hao defined that *“Reading culture refers to habitual and regular reading of books and information materials”*. The purpose of reading culture is the value of reading content, habits and reading method. In short, reading culture is "what to read" and "how to read".

2.2.2 The relationship between reading and reading culture

According to writer Nguyen Huu Viem, the author of the idea *“reading culture is reading behavior, reading value and reading standards of individuals or communities”*. There is always a relationship between reading and reading culture. Reading includes reading habit, reading hobby and reading skill. If we rarely read, we cannot create a reading culture.

Therefore, reading habits and reading skills happen simultaneously while the reading hobby depends on specific individuals (education level and personal genius). For example, some people like to read poetry, some people like to read novels, some people like to read research books, others like to read popular books of science and technology, arts and culture. These elements create the diversity and variety of reading culture in society.

Considering the reading culture of each individual, if a person has a habit of reading, but lacks reading skills, he cannot understand clearly the book’s message. If the readers can master reading skills, but they do not create reading habits, they will not gain much knowledge, even lack necessary knowledge for their own lives.

2.3 Previous research papers

There are many researchers carrying out the theses about reading culture or reading habits.

Goforth (1976) conducted one of the earliest studies about the reading habits of Filipino students in which her survey focused on young adults from four high schools located in the Greater Manila. Respondents consisted of 435 third year level students who

were asked about their reading habits and other extracurricular activities. Findings showed that Filipino young adult females read more than young adult males. There are slight differences in the preference of reading materials among them. Females opted more for magazines while males preferred newspapers and comic books. Mass media seemed to have an influence on the reading habits of these young adults as many of the titles that they read have been made into movies. Students are also likely to read more if they have access to various reading materials. Whether extracurricular activities have an influence on the reading habits of students was unclear in the study.

In 1992, another study on the reading interests of 425 randomly selected students from the different colleges in Central Luzon State University was organized by lecturer San Juan. It focused on reading materials used by the students aside from textbooks and reference books. These consisted of fiction and nonfiction books, journals, magazines, newspapers and comics. Demographic factors such as age, sex, educational attainment of parents, economic status, and academic achievement of students were examined as possible influences in their reading interests. Finally, the findings showed that fiction and nonfiction books are the most favored materials for reading followed by newspapers, magazines, comics and journals. In conclusion, females were more likely to choose romance books, movie and picture magazines, while males opted for sports magazines and science and technology books. The common reasons given by respondents for reading were to increase knowledge, gain information, improve vocabulary, and improve reading comprehension.

In the article revisiting the Peter Effect (2004), Applegate surveyed 195 sophomores who were enrolling in certification programs in elementary education. Their aim was to determine their reading habits and attitudes, and to shed light on the influences that might have formed these attitudes. It was found that the students were not very avid readers and also did not enjoy the reading experience.

Two years later, in 2006, the writer De Dios conducted a study on the role of the library and its resources and activities, in the promotion of reading habits of school children. Specifically, she focused on the activities and resources of Aklatang Pambata and their effects on the reading habits of public school children who used them. It was implied that the children's library should be able to provide interesting books and activities so that children may be encouraged to read more. Promotional events and marketing of library services should also be utilized to further gain the support of schools and parents.

The lecturer Borja (2007) did a survey on the reading interests and habits of 119 freshmen students at the University of the Philippines Diliman who were taking up English classes on the second semester of academic year 2006-2007. The study was done in the context of the effects of pleasure reading on the students' performance in their classes. The survey revealed that respondents stated that the library's collections met their pleasure reading needs and that the library was conducive to studying. However, they seldom had their own reading pleasure although they indicated that the materials they read for pleasure help them in their English classes. The materials they preferred the most were fiction of which bestsellers was the favored sub-genre. They mostly borrowed

these materials according to frequency: textbooks/reference books, journals, newspapers, multimedia resources, and novels. The results also indicated that the most common reason for using the library was for academic purposes such as doing research and homework; pleasure reading was their last priority.

With the same idea of Goforth, Ajala - the author of the thesis "*Use of the University of Ibadan Library resources by graduate students*", (2008) researched a study on the use of the University of Ibadan Library resources by graduate students in the view of assessing whether library resources were used by the students and if they met the students' research needs. The respondents consisted of young adult students from various fields such as education, science, technology, arts, social sciences, and agriculture. Most of them indicated that they used journals as their main source of information, followed by textbooks, reference books, and theses and dissertations. A third of the respondents used the library either daily or twice a week; most of them spent one to two hours per library visit. They also used other libraries aside from the University of Ibadan Library. The study concluded by recommending that the library should engage in library user education, promotion of services to increase user awareness, and acquisition of books and journals which should be made accessible to students.

The writer of International Journal of Behavioral, Cognitive, Educational and Psychological Sciences named Oguz (2009) also carried out a survey of the reading habits of students who were taking up education – classroom teaching – in different Turkish Universities. It was held previously that young people, as well as teachers in Turkey did not have high levels of reading habits. It was found that the students seldom or rarely read books, stating the lack of time as their primary reason. Those who did read books expressed that they often read novels. It was surprising that more than a third (35.7%) of the respondents spent only an hour or less for reading. However, most of the respondents stated that they read newspapers regularly. It was also found that there was a slight difference in the reading habits of different genders; women were more likely to read, compared with men. Owning bookshelves had a positive effect on the reading habits of the students. In addition, reading time and level of reading habits were also positively correlated. It was concluded however, that these students still have inadequate reading habits and actions must be done to strengthen them.

2.4 How the reading culture affects learning outcomes

In 2007, professional teacher Su-Yen conducted a study on the extracurricular reading habits of first and third year Taiwanese college students. Factors such as gender, parental educational level, institutional type, and college major were analyzed to know whether they had an effect on the amount of time spent on extracurricular reading. Results indicated that male tended to read more than female for both levels. Third year students were found to read more than first year students. A comparison of academic skills between students with various types of institution (public or private) showed that students who had lower academic skills spent more time in extracurricular reading than those with better academic achievement. Interestingly, students with lower grades spent more time in extracurricular reading although students with the highest grade averages

remain as the group with highest amount of time spent on reading. Arts and architecture majors spent the most amount of time on reading. Humanities majors were avid readers and read more than natural science and education majors confirming Applegate and Applegate's findings (2004). Newspapers and magazines were preferred reading materials of the students.

Another study carried out by journalist Manansala (2009) on reading interests of high school students at the Parada High School. The respondents consisted of second, third and fourth year high school students. A majority of them indicated that they often read books. There are slight differences in the preference of reading materials among different levels. Second year students opted for newspapers, comics and magazines while third and fourth year students chose comics and magazines. Academic performance did not have an effect on the reading interest of the students. They read mainly to learn, gather additional information and support them in their academics. Students also indicated their top influence in learning: reading habit.

Chapter III: Materials and Methodology

The methodology presented in this chapter showed how this study was carried out. First, this chapter begins with some hypotheses. Then, it mentions the research design and the participants. This thesis is followed by research instrument with the result of the questionnaire in detail.

3.1 Hypotheses

According to the literature review and research questions, it was conducted that English majored students at Tay Do University realized that the reading culture was falling into oblivion as well as the importance of reading books. Therefore, they realized the significance of reading and then students would spend more time reading books.

3.2 Research design

The research was effectuated to investigate the reading culture of English majored students at Tay Do University. It was carried out with quantitative method. Participants provided real information by answering the questionnaires. Then, the data from questionnaires was analyzed to get the final result for discussion.

3.3 Participants

The participants were 100 English majored students of four classes including English Linguistic 10B, 11A, 12C and 13A at Tay Do University. There were 32 males and 68 females. Their ages ranged from 18 to 22 years old. They had different tastes in reading books and also gave me their opinions about the reading culture nowadays.

3.4 Instruments

To achieve the goals of the thesis, the research employed questionnaires for students. The research instrument was completely based on information gained from theories related

to issues in chapter two. The questionnaire was executed to show the students' thoughts on reading culture today.

3.4.1 Questionnaire

The questionnaire was used as the most important instrument because a large amount of information was collected from a huge number of people in a short period of time. Besides, the results of the questionnaires could be quickly and easily quantified by the use of the software package.

Based on literature review, research aims, and research questions. The questionnaire was designed with a 5-point Likert scale: (5) strongly agree, (4) agree, (3) demur, (2) disagree, (1) strongly disagree. It consists of 21 statements which are classified into the following groups.

Table 1: Classification of statements in the questionnaire based on their content

Group	Summary of the content of question group	Statements (Q)
1.	The idea of reading culture	Q1, Q2, Q3, Q4.
2.	The reality of reading culture	Q5, Q6, Q7, Q8, Q9, Q10.
3.	Some factors effecting reading culture	Q11, Q12, Q13, Q14.
4.	Some solutions to develop reading culture	Q15, Q16, Q17, Q18, Q19, Q20, Q21.

3.5 Procedures

In this part, the process of doing this research was presented. This research was conducted in 16 weeks and the process was divided into 4 steps as the following procedure.

Table 2: The process of the research

Duration	Activities
Step 1 The first four weeks	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Meeting the instructor and choosing the suitable topic - Making the outline of the study - Designing the questionnaire - Writing Chapter 1 and Chapter 2
Step 2 From the 5 th week to the 8 th week	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Contacting and asking teacher for the permission of delivering questionnaire - Writing Chapter 3 - Delivering the questionnaire to students to collect the data
Step 3 From the 9 th week to the 12 th week	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Analyzing the date collected from the questionnaire - Making the outline of Chapter 4
Step 4 The last four weeks	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Completing the research by writing Chapter 4 and Chapter 5

Chapter IV: Results and Discussion

The results of the questionnaire are shown in this chapter. The final results are drawn from analyzing the data collected from 100 English majored students in chapter III.

4.1 Results of the questionnaire

After analyzing the information in the questionnaire, the researcher got some results about student's reading culture which included 4 main parts: the idea of reading culture, the reality of reading culture, some factors affecting reading culture and some solutions to develop a reading culture.

4.1.1 The Cronbach's Alpha

In order to make the thesis more reliable, the researcher used the IBM SPSS Statistic 20.0 package software to analyze the data as well as get the Cronbach's Alpha. The Cronbach's alpha showed how the questions or statements in each group closely related to each other so that the "high" value of the Cronbach's Alpha results could become the evidence for the data measuring in this group under construction.

According to the questionnaire design, the Cronbach's Alpha presented was based on 4 groups listed in the questionnaire. The alpha coefficient of each group was $\alpha = 0.78$, suggesting that the items had relatively high internal consistency. The results meant that the statements in each group were closely related to each other.

4.1.1.1 The student's idea of reading culture

In the idea of reading culture, the questionnaire included 4 sentences (from Q1 to Q4) showing the student's opinion about the reading culture of English majored students. The majority of students considered that reading was very necessary, it had positive effects not only on learning outcomes but also on the whole life. Besides, the school library played an important role in developing reading habits or reading attitudes of students.

The graph illustrated that most students considered the importance of reading books, more than 80% of students had a positive attitude towards reading, they agreed that reading was an indispensable activity for their studying.

Figure 1: The importance of reading culture

4.1.1.2 The reality of reading culture

To know clearly about the real situation of reading culture, the researcher wanted to find out some reasons why undergraduates read books/newspapers/reference materials. These common reasons were shown in the figure below

Figure 2: Common reasons why students read books

As was shown in the column chart, nearly half of undergraduates (51%) read books/newspapers/reference materials for entertaining. Reading for entertainment was the first choice for students, they tended to spend more time for reading with entertaining purposes. It seemed that they read book for relaxing and reducing stress after a hard-working day. The second position belonged to school assignment with 39% of students who read to complete their schoolwork, in other words, they read books because of teacher requests. There were only 10% of participants asserting that they wanted to find new information or get more knowledge with reading activity.

Figure 3: Some common places where students read books

As the line chart shows, there were some common places that students chose to read books like home, coffee shop, school library, bookstore,.... Home can be chosen as the favorite place for reading with 54%. More than half of the students enjoy reading at home. Quiet coffee shops were the second popular choice for reading with 35%. Very few students thought that school libraries (4%) and bookstores (7%) were the best places for reading. Generally, reading at home seemed to be the first choice for students because they found that they could enjoy reading without anyone disturbing, they could read with no limitation of time. Home was the most comfortable place to do everything on our own. Moreover, coffee shops were also a familiar choice because of their airy and quiet atmosphere; students could try some delicious cakes and drinks while reading. That was why reading at home was in the first place in comparison with other options.

Table 4: Students' thought about how to read effectively

Statements	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
12. Students don't know how to read quickly without missing important contents	1%	19%	27%	45%	8%
13. Students don't know how to find essential information quickly when reading books or newspapers	3%	8%	30%	37%	12%

Thanks to the data presented in pie-chart 2, the researcher got more information about student's reading material resources. The responses revealed that most participants showed that they read books on the Internet. To be more specific, over two-thirds of the students (70%) found reading materials on the Internet. In addition, there were 19% of students bought themselves favorite books. In contrast, 11% of students like borrowing books, documents from friends or school libraries. Nowadays, the internet is increasingly developing, so a lot of books or newspapers are updated on many popular websites. People prefer to read online because of its convenience and low price, that is the reason why most readers get reading materials on the Internet. Besides, some books are too high for students to buy, so students rarely get their favorite books. In short, people seldom borrow books from friends or libraries because of the limitation of time as well as the difficulty of conserving books.

Figure 5: Some common tools which students choose to read

As is shown in figure 5, there were some common tools that students liked to read such as online newspaper, smartphone, e-book and printed books. Smartphone was used by most students (43%) because of its convenience and quickness. There was one third of the students liked reading online, actually, online newspapers were also searched on the internet through some smart devices such as smartphone, iPad, laptop... People were close to smartphone, so they got the habit of reading online newspapers. Meanwhile, the percentage of students reading e-book or printed book was not high. Specifically, a small amount of students (14%) used e-book because readers did not like paying money to read some bestsellers on this tool and more than 10% of the respondents were still faithful to printed books. This proved that there were few students who read “traditional books”.

Figure 6: Common kinds of books that students like to read

Based on the figure 6, it was not hard to see the participants liked to read comic most, which was nearly 50%. Many students read books to relax and reduce stress after a hard-working day, so comic was the first option for them. Additionally, there were 34% of students who preferred to read books, newspaper about hot social issues. When living in the integration economy, students should catch the social situation regularly, so this was

the encouraging signal for reading culture. Students did not seem to like reading science or academic books, 15% of students choosing this kind of books, because their contents is too difficult to understand as well as it requires academic knowledge. The rest of them (5%) loved other types of books such as, romantic books, honor books, novel...

Table 3: Common methods to read books

Statements	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
10. I often read books, newspapers and documents in the following ways:					
a. From the beginning to the end	1%	11%	31%	35%	22%
b. Choosing interesting / important / essential content to read	3%	12%	17%	51%	17%
c. Skimming throughout the book to get the main idea	0%	16%	28%	42%	14%

Discussing the first table, most students agreed with reading books from the beginning to the end (at 35%) while only 11% of them disagreed with this method. It is considered that students who love reading find it better to read a book in order to make them skillful and enjoyable with the majors of books. However, the percentage of people disagreeing may come from impatient boredom. Regarding to main contents to read in a book, 51% of them agreed with this approach, but 12% of them did not agree. This viewpoint is suitable for students who are always fastidious, they only choose to read the key part or climax. Finally, there were 42% of students agreeing that they skim throughout the books to get the main idea, this method may be used for students who are really good in reading but for 16% students disagreeing, this method is really right for a person to enjoy a good book.

4.1.1.3 Some factors affecting reading culture

Reading is one of the most fundamental skills human needs to succeed in life. Sadly, students - the next generation are very indifferent to reading books for some following reasons.

Figure 7: Some common reasons why students are lazy to read books

Taking a quick look at figure 7, as can be seen from the responses, there were 41% of students (41%) admitting that reading books is not as attractive as other means of entertainment such as the internet, music or movies... In fact, reading books requires much patience and also takes a large amount of time, so many students (33%) were very lazy to do this activity. When being asked about the format and content of the books, 22% of students agreed with the idea that the form and content of some current books are very boring, most of the writers played to the gallery and lost their own personality. Last but not least, the book prices are not the barrier which make students rarely read books, just only 4% of students disagreed with the book price because they thought that high quality books or printed books are unaffordable to them. Referring to the findings, it can be considered that most of the students did not get used to the habit of reading books, thus it seems strange and boring to them. Moreover, they thought when reading books, they do not have enough time to do anything.

Table 4: Students' thought about how to read effectively

Statements	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
12. Students don't know how to read quickly without missing important contents	1%	19%	27%	45%	8%
13. Students don't know how to find essential information quickly when reading books or newspapers	3%	8%	30%	37%	12%

From the table above, more than half of participants claimed that they did not know how to read effectively with namely 53% agree and 49% agree for statements 12, 13. Besides, there were a few students believing that they know how to read quickly without missing the main contents as well as how to find the key information quickly when reading with namely 20% disagree and 11% disagree through statements 12, 13. About 57% had no idea. With their problems of reading method, teachers should provide their students with any specific methods for reading and seeking information skills.

Table 5: Some common reasons that students seldom go to the library/book fair/bookstore

Statements	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
14. Some common reasons that students seldom go to the library/book fair/bookstore					
a. They don't know some necessary information about these places.	6%	34%	27%	31%	2%
b. They don't have time.	5%	28%	26%	35%	6%
c. They think that these places don't have the document that they need.	4%	35%	33%	24%	4%
d. They have no need to find document.	7%	31%	29%	32%	1%
e. Their friends seldom go to these places, so do they.	11%	23%	24%	35%	7%

Depending on the data of table 3, the researcher got more reasons why students rarely head to libraries, book fairs or bookstores. In statement 14a, most participants believed that students know accurate facts about libraries, book fairs and bookstores with namely 40% disagree (including 6% strongly disagree and 34% disagree. It can't be denied that students went to school since their childhood, they became more familiar with books, libraries and bookstores.

In statement 14b, 6% of the students strongly concurred and 35% consented to the idea that students have no time to come to these places. Current students are very busy with their homework, part-time jobs, individual work or other leisure activities. If they do not have any reading habit or reading pleasure, they hardly come to the bookstore or book fair. If they want to find document, they just use smartphones for searching.

In statement 14c, 39% of undergraduates assented that libraries, bookstores and book fairs have useful document. That was a good sign, students should understand clearly the great benefits of reading printed books as well as maintaining this habit.

Similar to the above statement, the deponents approved of students finding documents in bookshop, library or book festival with namely 38% disagreed (7% strongly disagree, 31% disagree) in statement 14d. It could be said that finding documents, obtaining more knowledge as well as cultivating themselves day by day are the prerequisite of success in life. In the last statement (14e), over one third of students (35%) reckoned they could not go to these places alone.

4.1.1.4 Some solutions to develop reading culture

Looking at the reality of the reading culture, many students said that re-establishment of reading culture must stem from ourselves, and that is a necessary mission not only for students but also for everyone. The researcher found out some following cures for the recovery of reading culture.

Table 6: Some measures to expend the reading culture

Statements	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
15. Discounting books with many incentives for students	0%	5%	7%	60%	28%
16. Improving the formats and contents of printed books	0%	0%	11%	59%	30%
17. Adding books and specialized documents to the school library	2%	0%	13%	60%	25%
18. The libraries need a section to introduce good books and reference materials	2%	2%	6%	60%	30%
19. The libraries need to have both printed books and e-books	2%	1%	11%	58%	28%
20. The schools need to organize many contests to introduce books and find good reading factors	2%	1%	16%	59%	22%

21. The teachers should provide their students with specific and helpful methods for effectively reading and finding documents	1%	4%	16%	53%	26%
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The above table includes seven statements in total which investigated students' common methods in developing reading culture.

In statement 15, nearly 90% of students quite supported the idea that discounting books for students or some incentives ways are preferable. Selling books with a wholesale discount and making them returnable via a book distributor are good ways for books to sell like hot cakes. Besides, it is a chance for disadvantaged students be exposed to their favorite books. Only 5% of the respondents disagreed with this method. They reckoned they would buy their beloved books without worrying about money.

Next, as for statement 16, about three-fourths of students (59% agreed and 30% strongly agreed) stated that improving the formats and contents of printed books is an intelligent way to attract more students to read books. The book cover evolved as a marketing tool. It had to grab your attention at first sight. For that reason, the best designed covers should be beautiful art pieces. Imagining that the book had both charming cover and meaningful content, all the readers could go back to the gold habit named reading books. Conversely, the remaining with 11% of the respondents gave no comments.

Continued with statement 17, most students (85%) believed that adding books and specialized documents to the school library is a helpful way to encourage students go there as well as to help them learn better. Students found that they met some difficulties in their major, so the academic books can provide a large amount of useful knowledge that makes these students improve their shortcomings. The minimal percentages of students (2%) disagreed with this measure. They showed that they could not understand clearly the specialist knowledge in these books.

In subsequent statement (18), 90% of the undergraduates considered that their school library needs a section to introduce good books and reference materials to help students find documents easily. Labelled shelves should be used in the school library such as, new items, bestsellers and types of books. Each bookshelf should contain one book genre. This helps students save much time finding books as well as get more time to read. Just 4% of students objected to this method.

In statement 19, it was the obvious fact that Tay Do University library has both printed books and e-books. That was the reasons why 86% of the students concurred with this statement, the 11% of students did not have a clue about this statement. Currently, students also choose two tools (e-book and printed book) for reading, so it's very convenient for them to go to school library and enjoy books with their favorite tool.

In the following sentence (20), over 80% of the students suggested organizing reading contests to encourage people to build a reading culture. Besides, they wanted to create some clubs which exchange old or diverse books and promote the latest books in the library to attract students. There were 3% of students not being interfered.

Lastly, the result from statement 21 showed that most of the participants consented to this solution, with 26% strongly agreed and 53% agreed. There were 16% of the respondents expressing the neutral attitude to this statement. Students often got some problems in finding materials and reading, so it was very nice of their teachers to guide them some specific useful ways for effective reading and information collection.

4.2 Discussion

Depending on these results in this chapter, although students' awareness of the importance of reading, especially reading printed books, also was raised (85%), students still did not know that they are the reason making reading culture fall into oblivion.

Let's debate about the reality of reading culture and some methods to refresh the reading culture of English majored students at Tay Do University. It cannot be denied that students are lazy to read books.

First, to encourage students to read books, parents must be the ones who create the reading habit for them from childhood. Currently, due to the busy life, many families follow their bread and butter and forget the development for children. They often give their kids expensive toys or smart devices for entertainment; they rarely direct their children to reading. The researcher hopes that parents should spend their valuable time guiding their children to read as well as to develop their reading habit from the young age.

Second, the school library lacks in books which students want to read. The majority of reading materials in the library is just textbooks which students have no demand for. Some kinds of books are not suitable for students' age or unrelated because some students do not understand the books with academic content. The researcher believes that school libraries need to have books for sex education, guide-books, history books, playbooks... These books will help students open their mind and get more experience for the whole life. Besides, libraries should establish a section to introduce good books and reference materials. Moreover, the schools ought to organize many contests to introduce good books and find outstanding reading factors, the teachers had better show their student some useful ways for effective reading or finding documents.

Third, the reading culture at university declines and changes because of the boom in information and communication technology. Reading culture has been overwhelmed by the attraction of the internet as well as entertaining platforms. Students only read documents, books, newspapers as teachers' request. Through the research, most students think that the development of the internet makes them no longer enjoy reading (70%). Reading books requires a great deal of patience and also time, so many people choose to find information on websites to be fast and convenient. With the access to Google, students can get necessary information they want. What's more, many friends also share that they are too busy with the curriculum, doing part-time jobs, hanging out with friends or participating in social activities ... so even if they want to, they don't have time to read. Additionally, the content and format of books are unattractive compared to other means of entertainment such as the Internet, music, movies and shopping...

Fourth, for those who do not like reading, they will assume that the book has too many words. In contrast, for those who love reading books, the problem is that the prices of many books are not affordable for students, especially attractive books that are both long and expensive. That kind of books can be neither read quickly at bookstores nor bought home.

Last but not least, there is a possibility that students do not distinguish between different types of reading. They feel that reading is for work, not for recreation. And that feeling changes their attitudes towards reading for entertainment.

Based on the real situation below, recovering the reading culture is an important mission not only for students but also for everyone. Reading is not merely about obtaining knowledge, it also has many other benefits. There are many studies showing that reading stimulates the brain to function well, vocabulary, expand vocabulary and improve memory. A good book can reduce anxiety and stress, boost concentration, analyze ability. Moreover, many people read books for spiritual purification. The researcher really hopes that after this study, students can spend more time reading printed books and maintain the activity on a regular basis.

Chapter V: Conclusion, Implications and Limitations

This chapter can be considered as the report of the study. Firstly, the conclusions of the study will be pointed out. Next, the implications and the limitations of the thesis will be presented. Finally, this chapter ends with some recommendations.

5.1 Conclusion

The research goal is to find out the common thoughts about the reading culture of English majored students in Tay Do University. It was hypothesized that the students could recognize that the reading culture is buried in oblivion, as well as, they could realize the valuable benefits of reading books and contribute reading culture development. There were 100 English majored students of four classes including English Linguistic 10B, 11A, 12C and 13A at Tay Do University. The instrument using in this thesis was survey questionnaire. The data from the survey questionnaires were statistically analyzed by the SPSS English version 20.0 package.

The questionnaires provided the information as well as the students' opinions towards their reading culture. It helped the researcher focus on their reading attitudes, their reading habits as well as students' taste of reading through many specific statements given in the questionnaire. As the result, the findings were illustrated the effectiveness of this study in helping students know clearly about the great boon to reading books as well as spend more time reading books.

The results of this research lay foundation for further study with a wider range of the participants. This study hopes to have a good effect on students' interests in reading books as well as in teaching methods so that reading attitude in Vietnamese classroom can be improved.

5.2 Implications

Industrialization and modernization affect all of the aspects in the social life such as politics, economy, education, culture... Our country is also being affected. Impacts are seen in the changes of economic structure, of the teaching and studying method, also in the changes through process, especially the reading culture.

Reading is an essential foundation for living and success. Based on the reality, the researcher implemented the investigation into some common thinking about reading culture.

The researcher drew some ideas of the reading culture first, this helps students recognize a wide range benefits of reading printed books. Next, referring to the reality of the reading culture, students can notice that the reading culture is fading away and human is a decisive factor leading to this problem. After realizing and understanding the important role of reading printed books, students can improve their reading attitude or create reading habit from now on. Besides, the researcher provided some students' reasons why they are lazy to read books and bring out some measures to attract undergraduates read books regularly.

5.3 Limitations

Despite the significant findings, it should be admitted that this study has the limitations as follows:

Firstly, it was the size of the study, the number of students participating is still limited with namely 100 students. Students had their own opinions about the reading culture, so it is hard for the researcher to figure out their common ideas.

Secondly, due to the limited time, the research was only completed in four months for all chapters, sections, tables of contents... especially questionnaire delivery. Although the researcher tried a best to conduct the thesis instrument, questionnaire delivery was already executed in four weeks.

Thirdly, this topic was quite new, the researcher met some problems in finding reference materials because very few studies related to reading culture. A great amount of time was spent on reading Vietnamese newspapers to collect information and ideas.

Finally, the data were statistically analyzed by the SPSS software. The researcher had some difficulties using this software. It took much time to acquire the feel of SPSS software.

Chapter VI: Recommendations for Future Research

It can be noticed that the topic of reading culture attracts little attention of other researchers. This study plays a role as a foundation for further research on the students' opinions about reading culture in larger environment, in the Mekong delta. Besides that, this research can be the background for other thesis on the reasons why students are lazy to read books or some factors affecting reading habit. These reasons would be mentioned in detail to help students determine their situation as well as improve their reading habit. The situation of English majored students at Tay Do University only illustrated parts of

the problem in the reading culture. Therefore, further research in this field should be conducted in larger population including English major students and non-English majored students.

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